

Group Therapy and Psychological Well-Being Among Male Survivors of Gender Based Violence (GBV) in Nakuru County, Kenya

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Abstract:

Psychological well-being is a desired state, but stressors like GBV often lead to challenges such as stress, anxiety, and depression. Male survivors of GBV face significant psychological difficulties, yet interventions for this group remain underexplored. This study examined the impact of group therapy on the psychological well-being of male GBV survivors in Nakuru, Kenya. Key objectives were to analyze GBV patterns, assess survivors' psychological well-being, and evaluate the effects of group therapy on self-acceptance, purpose in life, and interpersonal relations. Guided by Cognitive Behavioral Theory, the study employed a Quasi-Experimental

Research Design with "Group Therapy" as the independent variable and "Psychological Well-being" as the dependent variable.

A census approach was used to sample 119 participants, split into a control group from Nairobi Women's Hospital GVRC (56) and a treatment group from Love and Hope Centre (63). Data was collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scales. Instrument reliability was tested via test-retest at a threshold of 0.7, and analysis was conducted using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Volume 27 (SPSS v27), incorporating descriptive (frequencies, means, standard deviations) and inferential statistics (t-tests, ANCOVA).

Findings revealed a positive significant relationship between group therapy and psychological well-being. GBV predominantly occurred at home, with wives and concubines as primary perpetrators. Psychological abuse, threats, denial of sex, and verbal abuse were the most common forms of violence. The study recommends survivors form therapy groups for peer support, comprehensive assessments at treatment facilities including emotional and mental evaluations, and the integration of counseling into treatment protocols. Empathy, unconditional positive regard, and professional congruence are essential in managing GBV cases. Survivors are encouraged to champion awareness creation to reduce stigma and foster support within their communities.

Keywords: *Psychological Well-being, Gender-Based Violence, Anxiety, Depression, Male Survivor.*

Introduction

Across the world, men experience persistently high patterns of GBV without reporting for fear

of ridicule, thus encouraging the perpetrators of GBV against men (Cohen, 2019). GBV manifests in the form of sexual violence (SV),

Physical violence, and sexual harassment. Other forms of violence include Verbal, Socio-economic, and psychological violence. Most cases of GBV against men have been perpetrated as a consequence of various social factors including a lack of job by the husbands, arguments and lack of listening to each other, alcohol and substance addiction by the perpetrators, uncontrolled anger, and ego problems among others (Boughzala et al., 2017). Additionally, GBV against men manifests in the form of violence against partners within the LGBTI community as well as other forms of IPV and DV.

As with the rest of Africa, Kenya also appears to continue experiencing worrying patterns in GBV among men, a trend that continues to be disregarded by most human rights advocacy spaces. In Kenya, most of the cases of GBV against men are in the form of intimate partner violence (IPV). Such cases of GBV are always reported in terms of either sexual, physical, or emotional violence. Additionally, 12% of men often report multiple forms of violence such as a combination of domestic violence, and physical and sexual violence (GBVIMS, 2017; Onyango, 2016; USAID, 2020). Kenya Violence against Children reports that 20% of Kenyan boys have experienced sexual violence before they turned 18 years old. According to various Gender Violence Recovery Centers in Kenya, at least 5% of all men have experienced at least one form of GBV. A Maendeleo ya Wanaume report indicates that approximately 2.1 million men face some form of GBV daily in Kenya. Such violence is reported to be in the form of battering inflicting bodily harm. Further, a report by the Kenya Demographic and Health Survey (KDHS) indicates that GBV against men is on an increasing trend with 11% of the cases of married men being violence from intimate partners (IPV), 9% being physical violence and 4% being sexual violence.

In Kiambu County, 56% of all men have experienced GBV in the form of threats, denial of sexual, rationing of food physical assault, and battering (Mongare & Obonyo, 2018). In Kisii County, domestic violence against men has been widely reported in form of physical violence

(33.4%), psychological abuse (28.7%), verbal abuse (74.4%), denial of meals (44.2%), stalking (51.1%), issuance of threats (38.4%) and sexual violence in form of rape (10.2%), made to penetrate (6.5%, denial of sex (40.7%) and forced to inherit wife (4.7%) (Mokebo, 2018). In the Kenyan context, these studies were explorative and therefore did not indicate how the incidences of GBV against men affected their psychological wellbeing.

Materials and Methods

Research design refers to the methodological framework that is used to incorporate data collection, analysis, and communication of the results (Robbins, 2019). It forms the blueprint on which different research methods are used to meet the objectives of the study (Morgan, 2017). This study used a Quasi-Experimental Research Design with a control and experimental group. Experimental Research Design was used since it allowed for testing of the effect of pre-exposure to treatment as well as confounding variables (Neuman, 2014). The design was able to yield accurate results while taking care of all possible confounding variables in the study thus allowing a wider generalization (Latunde, 2016). However, to yield valid results, the experiment needed to be carried out in its natural setting to avoid artificiality criticism (Vanderstoep & Johnston, 2019). For this, the study was carried out among the male survivors of GBV in their Gender Violence Recovery Centres. The design used is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Solomon Four Non-Equivalent Control Group Design

Group	Pre-Test	Treatment	Post-Test scores
E	O ₁	X	O ₃
C	O ₂	-	O ₄

Key: E- Experimental Group; C- Control Group; O₁O₃- Pre-test Scores; O₂O₄- post-test scores; - - No treatment; X- Treatment.

The design facilitated the assessment of the effects of the experimental treatment (group

therapy) compared to the control treatment. The researcher conducted a debriefing for both groups at the end of the session.

Variables of the Study

Group therapy was the independent variable whereby support group therapy strategy was used. The independent variable was analyzed against the dependent which was the psychological well-being of male survivors of GBV. The study had four dependent variable indicators, namely; self-acceptance, personal growth, positive relationships, and purpose in life. Therapists' characteristics such as their work experience, education level, and attitudes toward group therapy were used as the confounding variables.

Location of the Study

The study was conducted in Nakuru City County, Kenya, which covers an area of 7,495.1 km². Located in the southeastern part of the Rift Valley Province, Nakuru County borders seven other counties: Baringo to the north, Laikipia to the northeast, Nyandarua to the east, Kajiado to the south, Narok to the southwest, and Bomet and Kericho to the west. It is situated at coordinates 0.4254° S, 36.0023° E, with a latitude of 0° 16' 60.00" N and a longitude of 36° 03' 60.00" E. Administratively, Nakuru County is divided into eleven sub-counties and 55 wards. The county has a population of 2,162,202, with an annual growth rate of 3.0% and a population density of 289.7/km². The male population is 1,077,272, while the female population is 1,084,835 (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, 2019).

Target Population

The target population refers to the group of people or objects from which a representative sample is selected is selected for generalization (Clements & Sarama, 2016). The study targeted male survivors of GBV in Nakuru County, Kenya, and whereby the inclusion criteria were male individuals who had a history of GBV, had no co-occurring issues with drug abuse, and were not in the rehabilitation program. The male survivors of GBV were obtained from the Love and Hope Centre in Nakuru and Nairobi

Women's Hospital - Gender Violence Recovery Centre (GVRC) in Nakuru Branch. In Nakuru Branch, Nairobi Women's Hospital - Gender Violence Recovery Centre (GVRC) received 80 male survivors of GBV per month while Love and Hope Centre on the other hand received an average of 90 male survivors of GBV per month. Therefore, the target population was 170 male survivors of GBV. However, 70% of the male survivors of GBV were available for follow up and therefore the accessible population was 119 (70% of 170) male survivors of GBV. Table 2 shows the population distribution.

Table 2. Population Distribution

Center	Target population	Accessible population
Love and Hope	90	63
Nairobi Women	80	56
Total	170	119

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Sampling Techniques

Sampling technique refers to the procedures and techniques that are used that are used to select a sample from the target population (Robbins, 2019). The study used purposive sampling to select the two institutions; Love and Hope Centre in Nakuru and Nairobi and Women's Hospital's GVRC, Nakuru Branch. The criteria for purposely selecting the two facilities were because they had counseling services for survivors of GBV. The study selected all 119 male survivors of GBV in the two selected premises using a census approach. The census approach involves a complete enumeration of the study subjects thus presenting zero sampling error (Morgan, 2017). This method was used since there are only two facilities that actively deal with survivors of GBV within Nakuru County.

Sample Size

Sample size refers to the proportion of the target population selected to be studied for generalization to the entire population (Robbins, 2019). Since the study used a census approach, all the male survivors of GBV from the two

centers were selected for the sample. Among the accessible population of 119 male survivors of GBV, Love and Hope Centre had 63 survivors while Nairobi Women’s Hospital - Gender Violence Recovery Centre (GVRC) had 56 survivors. Since the study used the Solomon Four-Group Non-Equivalent Control Group Design, the Nairobi and Women’s Hospital’s GVRC was the control group while the Love and Hope Centre was the experimental group to avoid data contamination. Therefore, Nairobi Women’s Hospital - Gender Violence Recovery Centre (GVRC) comprised of two control

groups, that is, C_1 and C_2 while Love and Hope Centre comprised two experimental groups, that is, E_1 and E_2 . Within the experimental groups, group therapy was done within smaller groups of between 8-12 members. C_1 and E_1 were given a pre-test to establish their score on psychological well-being at the entry of the study. The post-test score of psychological well-being was standardized using pre-test results to control for entry differences in their psychological well-being. Table 3 shows the sample size distribution of various groups.

Table 3. Sample Size Distribution

Center	Sample Size	Group	Group Size	Therapy groups
Love and Hope Centre Nairobi	63	Experimental 1 (E_1)	63	-
		Experimental 2 (E_2)	63	6
Nairobi and Women’s Hospital’s GVRC	56	Control 1 (C_1)	56	-
		Control 2 (C_2)	56	-
Total	119		119	6

Therefore, there will be a total of six therapy groups for the experimental groups whereby all the respondents were given a similar pretest and after six weeks the same test was then administered though E_2 had already been taken through group therapy while C_2 had not been exposed to group therapy.

Instruments of Data Collection

This study applied a structured questionnaire for male survivors of GBV. This questionnaire was adopted from Ryff’s Psychological Well-being Scales (PWB). This PWB scale was applied to establish the psychological well-being of male GBV survivors. The questionnaire was applied to yield quantitative data for the study. In their study, Ryff (1995) adopted 28 28-point version of the PWB scale that rated respondents on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly disagree to Strongly agree. The aspects used in the PWB scale included self-acceptance, personal relationships, personal growth, and purpose of life. The validity of the PWB scale was tested by Manyema et al. (2018). These researchers noted a reliability level of 0.902 while using the 28 items of the PWB scale. The negative statements in the PWB scale were reversed during data

collection to ensure data uniformity. The questionnaire also included basic metadata of respondents including marital status, age, educational levels, and employment status.

During the study, researcher administered Ryff’s PWB Scales to both the experimental and control groups before the intervention to establish baseline psychological well-being levels. In the post-test period, we re-administered the scales after the intervention to assess changes in well-being attributable to group therapy. The tool comprises six core dimensions of psychological well-being, with items designed to measure each dimension including self-acceptance, positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, and purpose of life. By using Ryff’s PWB Scales, the study ensures robust and credible measurement of the psychological well-being of male survivors of GBV in Nakuru County.

In addition, the study carried out Focused Group Discussion (FGDs) among the male survivors of GBV in the GBV Recovery Centre at Nairobi Women’s Hospital in Nakuru Branch and from Love and Hope Centre. From the FGDs, the study was able to obtain qualitative

data on the GBV the men experienced and also the psychological challenges they experienced as a result of GBV. The study also carried out interview schedules for counselors and psychologists from the Love and Hope Centre as key informants. These key informants provided qualitative information on patterns around GBV against men and also their psychological well-being in terms of self-acceptance, personal relationships, personal growth, and purpose in the life of male survivors of GBV.

Pilot Study

A pilot study is a small-scale study done before the actual study to establish the feasibility and viability of the study (Miller & Whicker, 2017). The study sought to ascertain the validity and reliability of the research instruments through a pilot study. A pilot study was carried out among male survivors of GBV from GBV Recovery Centre (GBVRC) in Kiambu Sub-County Hospital. The center had similar characteristics as GBV Recovery Centre at Nairobi Women's Hospital in Nakuru Branch and Love and Hope Centre in Nakuru in that it offered psychotherapy and social services to the survivors besides the court and medical services and received an average of 10 survivors a day (Chelangat, 2016). The pilot sample size was 12 male survivors of GBV from the GBV Recovery Centre (GBVRC) at Kiambu Sub-County Hospital. The 12 survivors represented 10% of the sample size (10% of 119) of the study as recommended by Kara (2015). The pilot study was carried out using the same methodology as this study.

Validity of Research Instruments

Instrument validity references the data collection tools' accuracy in obtaining the required data (Kunisch *et al.*, 2018). This study used Ryff's Psychological Well-Being Scales (PWB) whose validity level had been reported to be 0.902 to guarantee the content validity of the instruments (Sloan & Quan-Haase, 2017). The study also guaranteed content validity by developing the questionnaire from the study objectives. In addition, the instruments were subjected to thorough scrutiny from existing research as well

as the supervisors of the current study. Constructive feedback from the supervisors and other research experts were considered in improving the instruments.

Reliability of Research Instruments

Research instrument reliability refers to the ability to reproduce similar results when measurements are repeated under identical research conditions (Bryman, 2015). Data from the piloting involving 12 male survivors of GBV from the GBV Recovery Centre (GBVRC) at Kiambu Sub-County Hospital will be used to estimate the reliability of the instruments. The study used a test-retest methodology whereby the questionnaire was administered to the same respondents twice within 14 days. The feedback obtained in the two tests was correlated to check consistency using a two-tailed Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r). According to Almalki and Arabia (2016), a test and retest Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of at least 0.70 would be considered appropriate and did indicate that the instrument was adequately reliable and hence suitable for the study.

Data Collection Procedures

Before beginning data collection, the researcher obtained an introductory letter from Kenyatta University. In addition, a research permit was sought from the National Commission for Science, Technology, and Innovation (NACOSTI), which authorized the researcher to collect data within Nakuru County. The researcher also visited Nairobi Women's Hospital's Gender Violence Recovery Centre (GVRC) in Nakuru and the Love and Hope Centre to request permission to collect data at their facilities. After receiving approval from the management of both centers, the researcher organized the experimental and control groups using the list of registered male survivors of GBV. Nairobi Women's Hospital - GVRC Nakuru Branch served as the control group, while the Love and Hope Centre was designated as the experimental group to prevent data contamination. Consequently, group therapy was conducted exclusively at the Love and Hope Centre.

A pre-test was carried out on both the control and experimental groups to establish their psychological well-being level at entry to the study. Then the therapy session was carried out for three months for the experimental group (Love and Hope Centre) whereby the researcher who was a certified psychologist was the group therapist. Across the three months of the experiment, the male survivors of GBV from the Love and Hope Centre underwent three group therapy sessions; one each month at a day that was agreeable among the group members. Upon completion of the three months, both experimental and control groups were examined for their change in psychological well-being. However, debriefing of the participants was done before and after the experiment to establish whether to ascertain if there was any negative influence of the treatment and breach of ethical considerations.

Data Analysis and Presentation

The researcher cleaned and coded the data before the onset of the analysis. The researcher then started both descriptive and inferential analysis of the data using SPSS Version 27. Descriptive statistics analyzed included mean, frequency, and standard deviations. Inferential statistics included ANCOVA and t-test at a 5% significance level. Specifically, the T-test was used to compare scores between two groups while ANCOVA was used to standardize scores based on pre-test scores of psychological well-being of male survivors of GBV to control for entry-level differences in the psychological well-being of the survivors. Qualitative data from interviews and Focused Group Discussions were analyzed using NVivo version 14. For qualitative data analysis, content analysis was done on emerging themes. The study findings were presented in the form of charts, tables, and narrative form. The summary of data analysis is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of Data Analysis

Question / Hypothesis	Variables	Statistical Tools
1. What is the prevalence of GBV against men among male survivors of GBV in Nakuru Country, Kenya	GBV	Descriptive Statistics Frequencies Means Standard Deviations Thematic Analysis
2. What is the extent of psychological wellbeing of male survivors of GBV in Nakuru Country, Kenya	Psychological Wellbeing	Descriptive Statistics Frequencies Means Standard Deviations Thematic Analysis
H0 ₁ : There is no statistically significant effect of group therapy on psychological wellbeing among male survivors of GBV in Nakuru Country, Kenya	Group Therapy Psychological Wellbeing	Means t-test ANCOVA

Results

Summary of Data Analysed as Descriptively and Inferentially using Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 27

This section shows a summary of findings that have already been discussed, data was run on

Excel and SPSS version 27 and results were compared to determine the reliability and validity of the responses as shared. The aim was to give a descriptive analysis of the data in the form of mean, median, and mode.

Table 5. SPSS-Location of GBV

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid %	C.F
Valid	Home	36	57.1	85.7	85.7
	Workplace	4	6.3	9.5	95.2
	Public places	1	1.6	2.4	97.6
	On transit	1	1.6	2.4	100
	Total	42	66.7	100	
Missing system		21	33.3		
Total		63	100		

The results shown above agree with those obtained from pre- and post-assessment of the control and experiment groups, focused group

discussions, and interview guides that have shown the home environment as the location with the highest incidences of GBV.

Table 6. Descriptive Presentation of the Location of GBV

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	M	Std. deviation	variance	skewness	error
Location	57	4	1	5	3.98	.790	.625	-1.318	.316
Valid	57								

Effect of group therapy on Psychological Wellbeing among male survivors of GBV

Table 7 below shows Pearson moment of correlation that sort to respond to the third objective of finding out the effect group therapy

has on the psychological well-being of the respondents in this case only 63 respondents were interviewed because they were in the experiment group hence were taken through group therapy and assessed before therapy and after therapy.

Table 7. FGD-Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Psychological Well-Being

Model	R ² change	F change	Df1	Df2	Sig.F change
1	0.27	1.116	1	40	.297

Table 7 above shows a P-value of .027 thus an indication that there is a positive statistical relationship between group therapy and psychological well-being.

Standard deviation results on the effectiveness of group therapy on psychological Wellbeing

The standard deviation of .465 indicates that the curve is normal hence results and feelings of the respondents on the effectiveness of group therapy on psychological well-being are within the curve thus sensible.

Table 8. Standard Deviation on the Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Psychological Well-Being from Focused Group Discussion

N	Valid	63
	Missing	0
Mean		1.90
Median		2.00
Mode		2
Std. deviation		.465
Variance		.217
Skewness		.349
Std. error of skewness		.302

Table 9. FGD-Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Psychological Well-being

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Highly effective	10	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Effective	49	77.8	77.8	93.7
	Not effective	4	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	63	100.0	100.0	

From Table 9 the study confirmed that group therapy is effective in improving psychological wellbeing where 15.9% of the respondents suggested it was highly effective, 77.8% effective and only 6.3% of the respondents felt it was not effective as they had hoped. In total 93.7% of the respondents felt it was effective.

Table 10 shows the correlation coefficient of the two variables the independent variable being group therapy while the dependent variable being psychological well-being.

Table 10. Pearson Correlation Coefficient between Psychological Well-Being and Group Therapy

		Psychological Wellbeing	Group therapy
Pearson Correlation	Psychological Wellbeing	1.000	.185
	Group therapy	.185	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Psychological Wellbeing	.	.073
	Group therapy	.073	.
N	Psychological Wellbeing	63	63
	Group therapy	63	63

Table 10 shows the correlation coefficient of 0.185 hence indicating that group therapy has a positive statistically significant relationship on Psychological Wellbeing and thus group therapy impacts Psychological Wellbeing positively.

Analysis of Covariance for the Relationship between Group Therapy and Psychological Well-Being among Male Survivors of GBV in the Experimental Group

Table 11 shows that there was a statistically significant positive relationship between group therapy and psychological well-being explained by the positive R-value.

Table 11. Descriptive Analytics on Indicators of Psychological Well-Being from FGD

Model	R square change	F change	Df1	Df2	Sig . F change
1	.034 ^a	2.160	1	61	.147

Table 11 above shows the mean, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, and skewness of indicators of psychological well-being as noted from the focused group discussions.

Table 12 below shows how group therapy influences the indicators of psychological wellbeing.

Table 12. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Specific Indicators of Psychological Wellbeing

FGD-Psychological Wellbeing		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Positive relations	4	6.3	6.3	6.3
	Personal growth	6	9.5	9.5	15.9
	Purpose in life	3	4.8	4.8	20.6
	Self-acceptance	4	6.3	6.3	27.0
	All areas	42	66.7	66.7	93.7
	None	4	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	63	100.0	100.0	

Most respondents reported that they had benefited in all areas listed above at 66.7%, 9.5% singled out personal growth, positive relations, and self-acceptance at 6.3% while purpose in life at 4.8%. It is only 6.3% of the respondents who reported that group therapy was not effective.

Figure 1 supports the explanation given in Table 12 above.

Table 13 shows the effectiveness of group therapy on positive relations.

Figure 1. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Specific Indicators of Psychological Wellbeing

Table 13. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Positive Relations

FGD-Positive Relations		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Highly effective	10	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Effective	49	77.8	77.8	93.7
	Not effective	4	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	63	100.0	100.0	

15.9% and 77.8% of the respondents reported that it was highly effective and effective respectively while only 6.3% stated that it was not effective. This supported the study (Gao,2018) that suggested group therapy had a positive impact on positive relations.

Figure 2 supports the explanation given in Table 13 above.

Table 14 shows the effectiveness of group therapy on personal growth among the respondents in the experimental group.

Figure 2. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Positive Relations

Figure 3. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Personal Growth

Table 14. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Personal Growth

FGD-Personal growth					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Highly effective	10	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Effective	49	77.8	77.8	93.7
	Not effective	4	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	63	100.0	100.0	

15.9% and 77.8% of the respondents reported that it was highly effective and effective respectively while only 6.3% stated that it was not effective. This supported the study (Ntete, 2017) that suggested group therapy had a positive impact on positive relations.

Figure 3 supports the explanation given in Table 14 above.

Table 15 below shows the effectiveness of group therapy on purpose in life among the respondents in the experimental group.

Table 15. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Purpose in Life

FGD-Purpose in life					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Highly effective	10	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Effective	49	77.8	77.8	93.7
	Not effective	4	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	63	100.0	100.0	

15.9% and 77.8% of the respondents reported that it was highly effective and effective respectively while only 6.3% stated that it was not effective. This supported the study (Quing, 2021) that suggested group therapy had a positive impact on positive relations.

Figure 4 supports the explanation given in Table 15 above.

Table 16 shows the effectiveness of group therapy on self-acceptance among the respondents in the experimental group.

Figure 4 Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Purpose in Life

Figure 5. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Self-Acceptance

Table 16. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Self-Acceptance

FGD-Self Acceptance		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Highly effective	10	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Effective	49	77.8	77.8	93.7
	Not effective	4	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	63	100.0	100.0	

15.9% and 77.8% of the respondents reported that it was highly effective and effective respectively while only 6.3% stated that it was not effective. This supported the study (Najma,2018) that suggested group therapy had a positive impact on positive relations.

Figure 5 supports the explanation given in Table 16 above

The data below shows the mean and standard deviation of group therapy, psychological well-being, positive relations, personal growth, purpose in life, and self-acceptance (Table 17).

Table 17. Descriptive Statistic

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
FGD-Psychological Wellbeing	4.37	1.348	63
Group therapy	1.90	.465	63
FGD-Positive Relations	1.90	.465	63
FGD-Personal growth	1.90	.465	63
FGD-Purpose in life	1.90	.465	63
FGD-Self Acceptance	1.90	.465	63

Table 18. Regression Analysis Correlation Coefficient for Descriptive Data

		FGD-Psychological Wellbeing	Group therapy	FGD-Positive Relations	FGD-Personal growth	FGD-Purpose in life	FGD-Self Acceptance
Pearson Correlation	FGD-Psychological Wellbeing	1.000	.185	.699	.005	.365	.108
	Group therapy	.185	1.000	.181	.106	.404	-.191

	FGD-Positive Relations	.699	.181	1.000	-.043	.330	.106
	FGD-Personal growth	.005	.106	-.043	1.000	.330	.106
	FGD-Purpose in life	.365	.404	.330	.330	1.000	-.266
	FGD-Self Acceptance	.108	-.191	.106	.106	-.266	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	FGD-Psychological Wellbeing	.	.073	.000	.485	.002	.200
	Group therapy	.073	.	.078	.203	.001	.066
	FGD-Positive Relations	.000	.078	.	.370	.004	.203
	FGD-Personal growth	.485	.203	.370	.	.004	.203
	FGD-Purpose in life	.002	.001	.004	.004	.	.018
	FGD-Self Acceptance	.200	.066	.203	.203	.018	.
N	FGD-Psychological Wellbeing	63	63	63	63	63	63
	Group therapy	63	63	63	63	63	63
	FGD-Positive Relations	63	63	63	63	63	63
	FGD-Personal growth	63	63	63	63	63	63
	FGD-Purpose in life	63	63	63	63	63	63
	FGD-Self Acceptance	63	63	63	63	63	63

Table 18 denotes that psychological well-being can be influenced by personal growth, purpose in life, self-acceptance, and positive relations. Of the 4 indicators positive relations have the greatest predictor effect at .699, followed by purpose in life .365, self-acceptance .108, and lastly .005 for personal growth. Group therapy on the other hand can be influenced positively

by positive relations at .181, personal growth at .106, purpose in life at .404, and poor self-acceptance can harm group therapy at -.191 but group therapy positively influenced psychological well-being at .073. Positive relationship was highly influenced by purpose in life at .330. Personal growth was however influenced highly by purpose in life at .330.

Table19. Descriptive statistics on the Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Indicators of Psychological Well-Being from the Interview Guide

Coefficients

Model		95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations		
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part
1	(Constant)	-2.528	1.450			
	Group therapy	-.534	.641	.185	.024	.017
	FGD-Positive Relations	1.195	2.386	.699	.624	.554
	FGD-Personal growth	-.728	.459	.005	-.060	-.042
	FGD-Purpose in life	-.122	1.258	.365	.213	.152

	FGD-Self Acceptance	-.292	.887	.108	.132	.093
a. Dependent Variable: FGD-Psychological Wellbeing						

The results below show the mean, median, mode, standard deviation, and variance of psychological well-being, and its four indicators

which include; positive relations, personal growth, purpose in life, and self-acceptance.

Table 20. Effectiveness of Group Therapy as Reported from the Interview Guide

		IG-Psychological Wellbeing	IG-Positive Relations	IG-Personal Growth	IG-Purpose in Life	IG-Self Acceptance
N	Valid	6	6	6	6	6
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		5.00	1.67	1.67	1.67	1.67
Median		5.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Mode		5	2	2	2	2
Std. Deviation		.000	.516	.516	.516	.516
Variance		.000	.267	.267	.267	.267
Std. Error of Skewness		.845	.845	.845	.845	.845
Skewness			-.968	-.968	-.968	-.968

The results show consistency in all the variables that were tested.

Table 21 below shows responses on the effectiveness of group therapy as reported by the six professionals during their interview.

Table 21. Effectiveness of Group Therapy as Reported by the Six Professionals During Their Interview

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	6	100	100	100

The results above suggest that they all noted that group therapy had had a significant effect on the psychological well-being of the respondents in the experimental group.

Table 22 below shows responses on the effectiveness of group therapy on positive relations as reported in the interview guide.

Table 22. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Positive Relations as Reported in the Interview Guide

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	6	100	100	100

The results above suggest that 33.3% of the professionals suggested that group therapy was highly effective in the respondents in the

experiment group positive relations while 67.7% suggested that it was effective in improving positive relations.

Table 23 below shows responses on the effectiveness of group therapy on personal growth as reported in the interview guide.

Table 23. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Personal Growth as Reported in the Interview Guide

	Frequency	%	Valid percentage	Cumulative %
Highly effective	2	33.3	33.3	33.3
Effective	4	66.7	66.7	66.7
Total	6	100	100	100

The results above suggest that 33.3% of the professionals suggested that group therapy was highly effective in the respondents in the experiment group personal growth while 67.7% suggested that it was effective in improving personal growth.

Table 24 below shows responses on the effectiveness of group therapy on purpose in life as reported in the interview guide.

Table 24. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Purpose in Life as Reported in the Interview Guide

	Frequency	%	Valid percentage	Cumulative %
Highly effective	2	33.3	33.3	33.3
Effective	4	66.7	66.7	66.7
Total	6	100	100	100

The results above suggest that 33.3% of the professionals suggested that group therapy was highly effective in the respondents in the experiment group purpose in life while 67.7% suggested that it was effective in improving purpose in life.

Table 25 below shows responses on the effectiveness of group therapy on self-acceptance as reported in the interview guide.

Table 25. Effectiveness of Group Therapy on Self-Acceptance as Reported in the Interview Guide

	Frequency	%	Valid percentage	Cumulative %
Highly effective	2	33.3	33.3	33.3
Effective	4	66.7	66.7	66.7
Total	6	100	100	100

The results above suggest that 33.3% of the professionals suggested that group therapy was highly effective in the respondents in the experiment group self-acceptance while 67.7% suggested that it was effective in improving self-acceptance.

The data below shows the mean and standard deviation as reported by the 6 respondents in the interview guide. It also shows the correlation coefficient between group therapy and psychological well-being which is indicated by 4 indicators namely: positive relations, personal growth, purpose in life, and self-acceptance.

Table 26. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Coefficient as Noted in the Interview Guide between Group Therapy and Psychological Wellbeing

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
IG-Psychological Wellbeing	5.00	.000	6
IG-Positive Relations	1.67	.516	6
IG-Personal Growth	1.67	.516	6
IG-Purpose in Life	1.67	.516	6
IG-Self Acceptance	1.67	.516	6

Table 27. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Coefficient as Noted in the Interview Guide between Group Therapy and Psychological Wellbeing

		IG-Psychological Wellbeing	IG-Positive Relations	IG-Personal Growth	IG-Purpose in Life	IG-Self Acceptance
Pearson Correlation	IG-Psychological Wellbeing	1.000
	IG-Positive Relations	.	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
	IG-Personal Growth	.	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
	IG-Purpose in Life	.	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
	IG-Self Acceptance	.	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	IG-Psychological Wellbeing	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	IG-Positive Relations	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	IG-Personal Growth	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	IG-Purpose in Life	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	IG-Self Acceptance	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	IG-Psychological Wellbeing	6	6	6	6	6
	IG-Positive Relations	6	6	6	6	6
	IG-Personal Growth	6	6	6	6	6
	IG-Purpose in Life	6	6	6	6	6
	IG-Self Acceptance	6	6	6	6	6

From Table 26 it can be observed that the respondents felt that group therapy had a positive significant relationship on all the indicators of psychological well-being namely; self-acceptance, positive relations, personal growth, and purpose in life.

The findings analyzed using both Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Science Version 27 have shown that group therapy has a positive significant relationship with Psychological Wellbeing and effectively influences the indicators of Psychological Wellbeing as presented.

Discussion

GBV is still prevalent within Nakuru County and it affects men. This was evident because of the

respondents who were interviewed within the specified research period and also feedback that the researcher obtained from the focused group discussions and interview guide. It was also reported that physical abuse was what took most of them to the facilities however upon screening it was noted that other forms of violence were more common than physical violence.

On demographics, the study noted that most men who experience GBV were within 31-40 years whereas according to Erikson's psychosocial stage they are in their early adulthood and thus navigating around intimacy and isolation. This also supports the observation that most of the victims are married. They also have secondary education and are self-employed running their businesses. This therefore suggested that age, marital status, educational

level, and occupation are factors that ought to be considered when supporting male victims of GBV.

The study observed that physical, emotional, and psychological violence were the forms of GBV victims experienced. It also noted that psychological violence in the form of threats, verbal abuse, and denial of meals whereas made to penetrate and rape. It was observed that the male victims had not classified psychological violence as GBV until when they were made aware by the service provider screening them. This therefore suggested that a lack of awareness of the various forms of GBV had resulted in the underreporting of GBV cases.

The study observed that no significant change occurred in the psychological well-being of respondents if no intervention was undertaken though factors like social support and resilience could contribute to a few of the positive changes noted among the control group. This therefore helped conclude that enhancing social and spiritual support would help build resilience and gradually improve the psychological wellness of male victims of GBV.

Conclusion

This study explored the patterns of GBV against male survivors in Nakuru County, their psychological well-being, and the impact of group therapy as an intervention. The findings revealed that all participants had experienced GBV, with psychological and emotional abuse being the most prevalent forms, primarily occurring at home and perpetrated by close family members. Stress, finances, and unfaithfulness were identified as common triggers. The experimental group demonstrated significant improvements in psychological well-being, including personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance, underscoring the effectiveness of group therapy. These results highlight the critical need for targeted interventions like group therapy to support male GBV survivors and improve their psychological resilience.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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